

ADAPTING SOFT AND HARD WHEAT VARIETIES TO UNFAVORABLE CLIMATE CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *This article details the selection of resistant soft and hard wheat varieties to unfavorable climatic conditions (winter, diseases, and heat) of the external environment and the application of breeding processes related to preliminary sources of research.*

Keywords: *local epiphyticia, rust disease, SIMMIT and ICARDA*

The increase in the global population and the growing demand for food in developing countries intensifies the pressure for sustainable additional food production. Due to rapid population growth in developing countries, demand for wheat is expected to increase by up to 60% by 2050 (International Food Policy Research Institute).

Wheat rust is the most widespread disease in the Central Asia region, causing significant damage to wheat yields. The population in this region is among the highest consumers of wheat products, such as flour and bread, in the world. [1].

In Kazakhstan, yellow rust disease is a permanent natural focus of the southern and southeastern regions. In recent years, local epiphyticia of yellow rust on wheat were observed in 1992, 1999, 2000, 2002, 2005 [2].

Epiphytotic development of yellow rust was observed in all agroclimatic zones of wheat in the North Caucasus of Russia in 2001. In 2004 and 2008, the development of yellow rust reached 20-40%, and yield losses - 10-15%, especially in the southern foothills of the region.

In recent years, global climate change, including the rapid recurrence of the disease, has caused great damage to grain crops, negatively affecting the yield and quality of grain varieties with valuable agricultural traits and characteristics.

As mentioned above, the causative agent is *Puccinia striiformis* f.s. *tritici* yellow rust disease is the main factor of biotic stress of wheat in the Central Asian region, and in practice the most effective, economical and environmentally friendly method of protection against this disease should be used, taking into account the effectiveness of the donors of the varieties' genes. resistant to the extreme variability of the causative agent of yellow rust disease [1].

Disease resistance genes are the main guarantee of the resistance of the varieties being created, and the fact that there are many races of wheat and they are constantly changing also made it possible to constantly monitor the virulence conditions of plant genes. local races [1].

Uniformity of productivity can be achieved through varieties resistant to biotic stress and abiotic stress. To create a high-yielding wheat variety, researchers need to develop resistance to biotic stress. In most cases, high-yielding varieties become diseased after reaching the productive stage in the selection process, that is, a resistant variety loses immunity and becomes diseased [4].

Chosh A., Puste A.M. [3] high yields can be achieved not only by frequent watering or fertilizing, but also by choosing a variety suitable for the same natural climate. The productive accumulation of grain crops, the number of grains in an ear, the weight of 1000 grains can be affected by the agricultural background or the relief of the place on one site.

Nowadays, the main attention is paid to wheat breeding in Uzbekistan.

To create wheat varieties suitable for intensive technology is not aimed. The varieties created are productive, dormant and must be resistant and demanding of fertilizers. But now we need to increase the yield by 80-100 c / ha, we should focus on varieties adapted to specific characteristics and external environmental conditions for each region and giving a stable (stable) harvest in changing weather conditions of the region.

For this reason, one of the effective areas is the creation and selection of varieties suitable for the soil and climatic conditions of each region, and their introduction into production for the regions of the republic where there is a shortage of water.

Based on these problems and tasks, the selection of varieties and samples of soft wheat resistant to unfavorable environmental factors and rust diseases in the republic, and the creation of new local varieties with high grain yields on their basis is a clear way to solve these problems and tasks.

The studies were conducted in the field and laboratory conditions of the Lalmikor Research Institute of Agriculture. The soil of the experimental field on the territory of the State Agricultural University named after D. Yoldoshev, Central Experimental Farm, is a typical gray soil, the salinity level is low, groundwater is located at a depth of 10 meters. Soil fertility is 68%.

Phenological observations were conducted and analyzed in the field and laboratory. Monitoring and evaluation work was carried out using the methodological manuals of B. A. Dospekhov (1985), mathematical analyses of the State Commission for Testing Agricultural Crops (1989), and the All-Russian Institute of Plant Growing (1991).

Analyses were carried out according to the International Classification (SEV Triticum type 1983) of the Russian Institute of Plant Growing and physiological indicators in the physiology laboratory of N. N. Koyushko. Comprehensive physiological assessment of drought and spring resistance of winter wheat in the conditions of Uzbekistan (Methodological instructions. 1987, R. V. Udovenko, T. V. Oleynikova, N. N. Koyushko) was carried out. The diagnostic technique was determined by the survivability of the plant (drought-spring-salt-and frost resistance, 1970). In 2023-2024, more than 550 collection samples of soft and hard wheat of the international organizations SIMMIT and ICARDA were studied in the laboratory of plant physiology and primary raw materials.

It is known that it is important to be able to determine high yields of plants in certain natural and climatic conditions. Ideally, one variety can produce high yields under certain conditions, but in other conditions they can be very susceptible to natural stresses. Given this, it is of great importance to study the genetic characteristics of varieties for rapid adaptation to natural stresses in various local natural and climatic conditions.

It was studied on the 550 varietal samples in 2023-2024, 36 soft wheat and 44 durum wheat varieties showed a very low level of overwintering, and only 80 variety samples (>21%) were extremely resistant to overwintering. 124 varieties of samples (66 soft wheat, 58 hard) are resistant, 211 varieties of samples (41-60%) are moderately resistant, 102 varieties of samples (71-90%) are highly resistant, 15 varieties of samples soft wheat - 18 hard wheat varieties, a total of 33 samples of varieties with very high resistance (<90%) were found (Table 1).

During the years of research, it was noted that in healthy climatic conditions, the incidence of yellow rust in the variety samples is 5-80%.

On the varieties of soft and hard wheat, 39 (0-10%) were resistant to yellow rust, 67 (15-25%) were moderately resistant, and the remaining varieties, 30-80% of the samples, were weakly and strongly susceptible, i.e. resistant, as a result of the disease, (Table 2).

Table No. 1.
Characteristics of winter hardiness of varietal samples of soft and hard wheat (Gallaorol 2023-2024)

№ score		The number of variety samples		
		Soft wheat	Hard wheat	Total
	Common studied variety samples	324	226	550
1	Very low (>21%)	36	44	80
3	Low (31-40%)	66	58	124
5	Average (51-60%)	136	75	211
7	High (71-90%)	71	31	102
9	Very high (< 90%)	15	18	33

Table No. 2.
Description of susceptibility to yellow rust of soft and durum wheat accessions (Gallaorol 2023-2024)

№ score		The number of variety samples		
		Soft wheat	Hard wheat	Total
	Common studied variety samples	324	226	550
1	Not affected (>5%)	4	6	10
2	Highly resistant (5-10%)	10	19	29
3	Moderately resistant (15-25 %)	38	29	67
4	Weakly resistant (30-40%)	151	111	262
5	Absolutely intolerant (<50%)	121	61	182

These days, the world, including our republic, is experiencing a change in climatic conditions to high temperatures. Also, in recent years, the selection of new wheat varieties suitable for hot and dry climates and their introduction into breeding processes as a source has become relevant.

When determining the heat resistance of soft and hard wheat varieties in laboratory conditions, it was considered important to determine the level of seed germination and root growth in a 1% sucrose solution.

As a result of the study, 188 samples of soft and hard wheat varieties showed very low seed germination and root growth in this solution, including 126 soft and 62 hard wheat varieties. It was found that 129 varieties had low, and 80 varieties had high seed germination and root growth (Table 3).

The research showed that the samples were 53 varieties with a very high level of seed germination and root growth in a 1% sucrose solution, including 24 soft wheat and 29 durum wheat.

One of the important signs of heat resistance was the weight of a 1000-grain plant.

When studying the weight of 1000 grains of the variety samples in the year of research, the following results were obtained. In 36 samples of soft wheat and 24 varieties of durum wheat, the content of less than 30 grams per 1000 grains was found. In 85 samples of soft wheat and 47 samples of durum wheat, the content of less than 40 g was found. The sample consisted of 166 varieties of soft wheat and 112 varieties of durum wheat weighing 41-42 g.

Table No. 3.

Heat resistance characteristics of soft and hard wheat varietal samples (Gallaorol 2023-2024)

№ Score		the number of variety samples		
		Soft wheat	Hard wheat	Total
	Common studied variety samples	324	226	550
1	Very low	126	62	188
3	Low	71	58	129
5	Average	57	43	100
7	High	46	34	80
9	Very high	24	29	53

In 32 samples of soft wheat and 35 varieties of durum wheat, 43-45 grams were found. 13 samples of very high grain weight - 1000 grains, 5 varieties of soft wheat and 8 varieties of hard wheat were identified.

Table 4

Description of the weight of 1000 grains of varietal samples of soft and hard wheat (Gallaorol-2023-2024).

Score	Grain size	the number of variety samples	
		Soft wheat	Hard wheat
1	very small (<27g)	36	24
2	small (31-39g)	85	47
3	medium (40-42g)	166	112
4	large (43-45g)	32	35
5	very large (> 51g)	5	8
Total		324	226

As can be seen from the above results of scientific research, 33 samples of high winter hardiness, 39 resistant to yellow rust, 53 resistant to heat and 67 large with a weight of 1000 grains and in 13 varieties of soft and hard wheat from the collection area the original source was isolated and selected for preservation in the gene pool for future use in the selection process.

REFERENCES

1. Torakulov Kh.S., Shokirova D.Sh., Bozorov T.A. "Protective response of yellow rust genes of plants to local races of yellow rust of wheat in Uzbekistan" Eastern Renaissance: Innovative, Educational, Natural and Social Sciences (E)ISSN: 2181-1784 www.oriens.uz SJIF 2023 = 6.131 / ASI Factor = 1.7 3 (7), July 2023 81-89b.
2. Gasanov B.A. Wheat weed diseases in Uzbekistan and their control. - Tashkent: 2007
3. Chosh A., Puste A.M. 1997. "Effect of irrigation and grafting on growth and yield of wheat (T.Aes.) and lenti (Lens Culinars) in pure form and in intercropping systems". Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences. 67(12): pp. 571-574.

4. Pingali P. and P.W. Heisey. 1996. Cereal crop productivity in developing countries: Past trends and future prospects. In *Global Agricultural Science Policy in the 21st Century*. Melbourne, Australia: Natural Resources and Environment. pp. 51–94.